

The Criminology Curriculum: Its Relevance to the Jobs of the Graduates

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Abstract:- This study examined the relevance of the criminology curriculum of Isabela State University-Cabagan to the jobs of the graduates. Using descriptive design, data gathered from 134 criminology graduates comprising of 108 male and 26 female was analyzed using arithmetic mean, t-test, and ranking. Result shows that the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curriculum of Isabela State University is responsive to the jobs of its graduates and that the courses offered are practical to the real-world professions of the graduates. Likewise, the academic related activities of the criminology program are significant to the careers of the graduates. Moreover, findings displayed that there is no significant difference between the assessments of male and female graduates on the relevance of the academic related activities and criminology curriculum particularly law enforcement administration, criminal detection and investigation, criminal sociology, criminalistics, and correctional administration courses to their jobs. On the other hand, result exhibited a significant difference on the assessment of the male and female graduates on relevance of criminal law and jurisprudence course to their jobs. Finally, the graduates endorsed the inclusion to the criminology curriculum of the competencies such as computer related subjects, police operational procedure, communication subjects, driving and swimming, and stress management subjects.

Keywords:- Criminology curriculum, Academic related activities, Education, Relevance, Jobs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions acknowledge the significance of curricula in the operation of every course offered. Without a responsive curriculum, the institution cannot operate effectively and efficiently due to having no definite idea of what plan to be taught to the students. Thus, the goal of teaching a subject is to ensure to build the students to be capable of what they want to be after completing the academic program. Moreover, curriculum is essentially a series of activities and learning outcome goals related to each subject. It serves as a great map, outlining what the students can achieve including the methods on how goals must be obtained.

In addition, Rhode Island Department of education defines curriculum is a standards-based sequence of planned experiences where students practice and achieve proficiency in content and applied learning skills. Curriculum is the central guide for all educators as to what is essential for teaching and learning, so that every student has access to

rigorous academic experiences. The structure, organization, and considerations in a curriculum are created in order to enhance student learning and facilitate instruction. Curriculum must include the necessary goals, methods, materials and assessments to effectively support instruction and learning.

Further, the study of Bueno, D. (2017) revealed that the curricula of the private higher educational institution-graduate school from 2010 – 2015 in the Philippines are responding to the needs of various industries. Specifically, Administration and governance, curriculum and instruction, research, professional and cognate courses, student services, library, internet laboratory, interdisciplinary learning, and teaching/ learning environment are the school-related factors relevant to the current employment of the graduates. Meanwhile, communication, human relations, entrepreneurial, information technology, problem-solving, critical thinking, and research skills are considered relevant skills learned. Moreover, love of God, honesty, punctuality, obedience to superior, perseverance, creativity, professional integrity, unity, fairness, love for others, nationalism and being eco-friendly are the values evidently manifested in their workplaces.

Correspondingly, Toquero, C. and Ulanday, D. (2021) displayed that curriculum of the Mindanao State University-General Santos City is responsive to the present employment of its graduates and that the supply of graduates' educational skills are highly matched with the skills demanded by the industry. Besides, a university with a relevant curriculum can offer authentic practical work experience integrated in the subjects to capacitate the graduates to be job-ready to meet the demands of employers in the industry.

Likewise, Zainab, A.N., Edzan, N.N., and Abdul Rahman, S.S. (2004) asserted that content of the curriculum of the Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) at the University of Malaya is relevant to the current job of the graduates. In addition, graduates are satisfied with the courses indicating their perceived usefulness of information science related courses.

Besides, Bautista et al. (2020) displayed that the Criminology graduates considered the subjects police organization and administration with police planning, police patrol with police communication system, and traffic management with traffic accident investigation as very relevant to their job placement. Also, the criminology graduates obtained a very high performance rating from their respective employers in terms of commitment and credibility.

As regard to the above concepts, the Criminology program of Isabela State University-Cabagan Campus started its offering in year 2006 by virtue of the Board of Regents Resolution Number 14, series of 2006. The program outcomes of the course is to equipped its graduates with relevant knowledge, skills, attitude, and values shall be able to conduct criminological research on crimes, crime causation, victims, and offenders to include deviant behavior; internalize the concepts of human rights and victim welfare; demonstrate competence and broad understanding in law enforcement administration, public safety and criminal justice; utilize criminalistics or forensic science in the investigation and detection of crime; apply the principles and jurisprudence of criminal law, evidence and criminal procedure; and ensure offenders' welfare and development for their re-integration to the community. Besides, from year 2006 to 2018, the curriculum implemented is based on CHED memorandum order (CMO) # 21. series of 2005 having a total of 187 units particularly with six professional courses such as criminal laws and jurisprudence, law enforcement administration, criminalistics, criminal detection and investigation, correctional administration, and criminal sociology.

The program is now on its fifteenth year of implementation and has produced graduates who currently employed in the different law enforcement agencies such as the Philippine National Police, Bureau of Jail Management and Penology, Bureau of Fire Protection, and some are in the teaching profession. Besides, the program has received informal information related to the significance of the courses offered in the Criminology program to the current job of the graduates. From this, there is a need to assess the relevance of the Criminology curriculum to the job of the graduates.

The findings of the study will be beneficial to the following: the university administrators - the results would provide inputs and/or feedback to help in examining the respective program offerings and will also serve as guide for planning and curriculum enhancement to have a gender responsive Criminal Justice Education program which is traditionally and continuously male-dominated course; the criminology graduates- findings may serve as an avenue to help their alma mater improve and sustain academic offerings; the faculty members - outcomes would provide insights on their competencies and thereby lead them to adopt more effective and quality teaching methods and strategies, likewise, this will provide the necessary information as to the

strengths and weaknesses of the prospective graduates of the Criminology program; the students -findings may provide advance insight on the courses to be given focus; the community - this study would enlighten the members of the community on the contributions of the criminal justice education in attaining peaceful and progressive nation. At present, there were no researches focusing on the relevance of the criminology curriculum to the job of the graduates, hence this study.

➤ *Objectives Of The Study*

This study assessed the relevance of the criminology curriculum to the jobs of the graduates. Specifically, this study aimed the following:

1. To determine the relevance of the criminology courses to the jobs of the male and female graduates.
2. To define the relevance of the academic related activities of the criminology program to the jobs of the male and female graduates.
3. To find out if there is significant difference between responses of the male and female graduates on the above objectives.
4. To determine the competencies recommended by the graduates to be embedded in the criminology curriculum.

II. METHODOLOGY

Utilizing the descriptive method, this study employed 134 criminology graduates of Isabela State University-Cabagan comprising of 108 male and 26 female. In addition, respondents were those who have served at least three years as uniformed officer of the Philippine National Police. Arithmetic mean was used to figure out how relevant the criminology courses and academic related activities to the jobs of the graduates. In addition, t-test was applied to find out if there is significant difference between the assessments of male and female graduates, while ranking was employed to determine the competencies recommended by the graduates to be embedded in the criminology curriculum. Shown below is the four-point Likert scale to describe the graduates' assessments.

Arbitrary values	Range	Description
4	3.26-4.00	Highly Relevant
3	2.51-3.25	Relevant
2	1.76-2.50	Less Relevant
1	1.00-1.75	Not Relevant

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The relevance of the criminology courses to the jobs of the male and female graduates.

Table 1. The perceived relevance of the law enforcement course to the jobs of male and female graduates

Law Enforcement Administration	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Police Organization & Administration with Police Planning	3.79	Highly relevant	3.62	Highly relevant	3.71	Highly relevant
2. Industrial Security Management	3.69	Highly relevant	3.69	Highly relevant	3.69	Highly relevant
3. Police Patrol Plan & Operation with Police Communication System	3.78	Highly relevant	3.80	Highly relevant	3.79	Highly relevant
4. Police Intelligence	3.71	Highly relevant	3.82	Highly relevant	3.77	Highly relevant
5. Police Personnel and Records Management	3.69	Highly relevant	3.85	Highly relevant	3.77	Highly relevant
6. Comparative Police System	3.35	Highly relevant	3.03	Relevant	3.19	Relevant
Category Mean	3.67	Highly relevant	3.64	Highly relevant	3.65	Highly relevant

The category mean of 3.65, indicating the “highly relevance” of the law enforcement course to the jobs of male and female graduates, implies that the subjects under law enforcement are responding to the professions of the graduates. Moreover, male graduates perceived higher assessment of 3.67 than female graduates having a mean of 3.64, which donates that law enforcement subjects are more useful in the performance of jobs among male graduates. Nevertheless, the subject comparative police system is perceived relevant as indicated by the area mean 3.19 suggesting that there is a need for a curriculum heightening to make the subject more useful to the graduates. This result is parallel to the findings of Bueno (2017), which revealed that the curricula of higher educational institution are responding to the needs of various industries.

Table 2. The perceived relevance of the Criminal Detection & Investigation course to the jobs of male and female graduates

Criminal Detection & Investigation	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Fundamentals of Criminal Investigations	3.82	Highly relevant	3.88	Highly relevant	3.85	Highly relevant
2. Traffic Management and Accident Investigation	3.71	Highly relevant	3.86	Highly relevant	3.79	Highly relevant
3. Special Crime Investigation	3.72	Highly relevant	3.85	Highly relevant	3.79	Highly relevant
4. Organized Crime Investigation	3.37	Highly relevant	3.72	Highly relevant	3.55	Highly relevant
5. Drug Education and Vice Control	3.69	Highly relevant	3.80	Highly relevant	3.75	Highly relevant
6. Fire Technology and Arson Investigation	3.20	Relevant	3.34	Highly relevant	3.27	Highly relevant
Category Mean	3.59	Highly relevant	3.74	Highly relevant	3.66	Highly relevant

The category mean of 3.66 shows the “highly relevance” of the Criminal Detection & Investigation course to the jobs of male and female graduates. This figure connotes that information acquired by the graduates along criminal detection and investigation subjects are beneficial in the performances of their professions. Besides, female respondents displayed higher assessment of 3.74 than male of 3.59, which signify that Criminal Detection & Investigation subjects are more utilized in the jobs female graduates. The findings is supported in the study of Bautista et al. (2020), which displayed that the Criminology graduates considered the subjects in the BS Criminology curriculum as very relevant to their job placements.

Table 3. The perceived relevance of the Criminal Law & Jurisprudence course to the jobs of male and female graduates

Criminal Law & Jurisprudence	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Criminal Law 1	3.68	Highly relevant	3.87	Highly relevant	3.78	Highly relevant
2. Criminal Law 2	3.74	Highly relevant	3.87	Highly relevant	3.81	Highly relevant
3. Criminal Procedure	3.80	Highly relevant	3.87	Highly relevant	3.84	Highly relevant
4. Criminal Evidence	3.76	Highly relevant	3.74	Highly relevant	3.75	Highly relevant
5. Court Testimony	3.69	Highly relevant	3.85	Highly relevant	3.77	Highly relevant
Category Mean	3.73	Highly relevant	3.84	Highly relevant	3.79	Highly relevant

The category mean of 3.79, reflecting the “highly relevance” of the criminal law and jurisprudence course to the jobs of male and female graduates, denotes that the learned knowledge from the BS Criminology curriculum along criminal law and jurisprudence is utilized by the graduates in the performance of their jobs. Further, female respondents exhibited higher rating of 3.84 than male of 3.73, this data entails that criminal law and jurisprudence subjects have greater applicability among female graduates. This output is matching to the study of Toquero, C. and Ulanday, D. (2021), which displayed that curriculum of the Mindanao State University-General Santos City is responsive to the present employment of its graduates and that the supply of graduates’ educational skills are highly matched with the skills demanded by the industry.

Table 4. The perceived relevance of the Criminal Sociology course to the jobs of male and female graduates

Criminal Sociology	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Introduction to Criminology and Psychology of Crimes	3.78	Highly relevant	3.78	Highly relevant	3.78	Highly relevant
2. Philippine Criminal Justice System	3.73	Highly relevant	3.82	Highly relevant	3.78	Highly relevant
3. Police Ethics and Community Relation	3.87	Highly relevant	3.88	Highly relevant	3.88	Highly relevant
4. Juvenile Delinquency and Crime Prevention	3.15	Relevant	3.81	Highly relevant	3.48	Highly relevant
5. Human Behavior and Crisis Management	3.57	Highly relevant	3.83	Highly relevant	3.70	Highly relevant
6. Criminological Research and Statistics	2.86	Relevant	3.16	Relevant	3.01	Relevant
Category Mean	3.49	Highly relevant	3.71	Highly relevant	3.60	Highly relevant

The category mean of 3.60 indicates that the criminal sociology course of BS Criminology curriculum is highly relevant to the jobs of the male and female graduates. This result magnifies the high applicability of the acquired learnings of the graduates on criminal sociology to their jobs. Moreover, female respondents exposed higher assessment of 3.71 than male of 3.49, this data infers that criminal sociology course is more practical among female respondents. Nonetheless, the subject criminological research and statistics is perceived relevant as reflected in the area mean 3.01 suggesting a need for curriculum enhancement to align the subject to the needs of the graduates. This finding is supported in the study of Zainab, A.N., Edzan, N.N., and Abdul Rahman, S.S. (2004), which asserted that the content of the curriculum of the Master of Library and Information Science (MLIS) at the University of Malaya is relevant to the current job of the graduates.

Table 5. The perceived relevance of the Criminalistics course to the jobs of male and female graduates

Criminalistics	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Personal Identification	3.22	Relevant	3.59	Highly relevant	3.41	Highly relevant
2. Police Photography	2.84	Relevant	3.05	Relevant	2.95	Relevant
3. Forensic Ballistics	3.58	Highly relevant	3.68	Highly relevant	3.63	Highly relevant
4. Questioned Document Examination	2.97	Relevant	2.9	Relevant	2.94	Relevant
5. Polygraphy	2.69	Relevant	2.84	Relevant	2.77	Relevant
6. Legal Medicine	3.48	Highly relevant	3.65	Highly relevant	3.57	Highly relevant
Category Mean	3.13	Relevant	3.29	Highly relevant	3.21	Relevant

The category mean of 3.21 directs that the criminalistics course of BS Criminology curriculum is relevant to the jobs of the male and female graduates. The female respondents revealed that criminalistics course is highly relevant to their job as showed in the 3.29, while male respondents viewed that the course is relevant to their job as indicated in the mean 3.13. This result infers that criminalistics subject are significant in the performance of jobs among graduates, nevertheless, the data suggests that there is a need for a curriculum enhancement on criminalistics course making the subjects more fitting to the prospect professions of the students. This result is influenced by the actual assignment of the graduates wherein no one among them is assigned to laboratory functions that require the use of criminalistics knowledge.

Table 6. The perceived relevance of the Correctional Administration course to the jobs of male and female graduates

Correctional Administration	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Institutional Correction	3.21	Relevant	3.13	Relevant	3.17	Relevant
2. Non- institutional Correction	3.20	Relevant	2.81	Relevant	3.01	Relevant
Category Mean	3.21	Relevant	2.97	Relevant	3.09	Relevant

The category mean of 3.09 displays that the correctional administration course of BS Criminology curriculum is relevant to the jobs of the graduates. Both male and female respondents regarded the course as relevant as indicated in the means 3.21 and 2.97 respectively. This result manifests that the knowledge developed by the graduates along correctional administration subjects are pertinent to their professions, though not in its fullest extent. Hence, there is a need for a curriculum enrichment to make the subjects under correctional administration course more practical to the future professions of the students. This finding is attributed to the actual job assignments of the graduates wherein no one is employed to the correctional institutions that require skills on correctional administration.

2. The perceived relevance of the academic related activities of the criminology program to the job of the male and female graduates.

Table 7. The relevance of the academic related activities of the criminology program to the job of the male and female graduates.

Academic Related Activities	Male		Female		Area Mean	DI
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI		
1. Reserve officer training corps	3.71	Highly relevant	3.73	Highly relevant	3.72	Highly relevant
2. Criminology Field Training Exercises	3.63	Highly relevant	3.60	Highly relevant	3.62	Highly relevant
3. Criminology student celebration	3.38	Highly relevant	3.30	Highly relevant	3.34	Highly relevant
4. Criminology Sports fest	3.52	Highly relevant	3.41	Highly relevant	3.47	Highly relevant
5. Emergency drills	3.62	Highly relevant	3.77	Highly relevant	3.70	Highly relevant
Category Mean	3.57	Highly relevant	3.56	Highly relevant	3.57	Highly relevant

The category mean of 3.57 reflects that the academic related activities of BS Criminology program are highly relevant to the jobs of the graduates. Correspondingly, the male and female graduates revealed that the academic related activities of the program are highly relevant to their jobs as exhibited in the category means of 3.57 and 3.56. This finding implies that the graduates have practically used the experiences picked up from the academic related activities of the BS Criminology program to their current professions.

3. Significant difference between responses of the male and female graduates on the relevance of criminology courses and academic related activities to their jobs.

Table 8. Difference between the responses of the male and female graduates on the relevance of criminology courses and academic related activities to their jobs.

VARIABLE	RESPONDENTS	MEAN	P-VALUE	T-VALUE	DECISION AT P<0.05
Law Enforcement Administration	Male	3.67	.822	.23	NOT SIGNIFICANT
	Female	3.64			
Criminal Detection & Investigation	Male	3.59	.258	-1.21	NOT SIGNIFICANT
	Female	3.74			
Criminal Law & Jurisprudence	Male	3.73	.016	-3.14	SIGNIFICANT
	Female	3.84			
Criminal Sociology	Male	3.49	.299	-1.11	NOT SIGNIFICANT
	Female	3.71			
Criminalistics	Male	3.13	.494	-0.71	NOT SIGNIFICANT
	Female	3.29			
Correctional Administration	Male	3.21	.381	1.47	NOT SIGNIFICANT
	Female	2.97			
Academic Related Activities	Male	3.57	.929	0.09	NOT SIGNIFICANT
	Female	3.56			

As shown in the table, there is no significant difference between the assessments of the male and female graduates on their subjects Law Enforcement Administration with p-value .822; Criminal Detection & Investigation with p-value .258; Criminal Sociology with p-value .299; Criminalistics with p-value .494; Correctional Administration with p-value .381; and Academic Related Activities with p-value .929. These figures conclude that the male and female graduates have analogous views on the relevance of the criminology courses and academic related activities to their professions. On the other hand, there is significant difference between the assessments of the male and female graduate on Criminal Law & Jurisprudence course with a p-value .016. This implies that the female graduates’ assessment on the subject Criminal Law & Jurisprudence is significantly greater than the male graduates.

3. Competencies recommended by the graduates to be embedded in the criminology curriculum.

Table 9. Competencies recommended by the graduates to be embedded in the criminology curriculum

Competency	Frequency	Rank
Computer related subjects	112	1
Police operational procedure subjects	92	2
Communication subjects	89	3
Driving and swimming subjects	83	4
Stress management subjects	75	5

The preceding table displays that most graduates recommended the competencies such as computer related, police operational procedure, communication, driving and swimming, and stress management subjects to be embedded in the curriculum of the Bachelor of Science in Criminology program.

IV. CONCLUSION

In view of the aforementioned findings, it can be concluded that the Bachelor of Science in Criminology curriculum of Isabela State University is responsive to the

jobs of its graduates. Hence, the courses offered in the criminology curriculum are practical to the real-world professions of the graduates. Likewise, the academic related activities of the criminology program are significant to the careers of the graduates. Moreover, there is no significant difference between the assessments of male and female graduates on the relevance of the academic related activities and criminology curriculum particularly law enforcement administration, criminal detection and investigation, criminal sociology, criminalistics, and correctional administration courses to their jobs. On the other hand, there is significant difference on the assessment of the male and female

graduates on the relevance of criminal law and jurisprudence course to their jobs. Finally, the graduates endorsed the inclusion to the criminology curriculum of the competencies such as computer related subjects, police operational procedure, communication subjects, driving and swimming, and stress management subjects.

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